

BEHAVIORAL DRIVERS OF DIGITAL DETOX ADOPTION AMONG MILLENNIALS IN SINGAPORE

Parvathy Subramaniam¹, Irina Pismennaya², Bhanu Ranjan³, Rahul Sharma⁴

¹EMBA Student & S.P. Jain School of Global Management

²Senior Academic Manager, Marketing & S.P. Jain School of Global Management

³Assistant Dean, Executive MBA & S.P. Jain School of Global Management

⁴Head of Data Solutions, Decube, EMBA & S.P. Jain School of Global Management

Abstract -This study aims to explore Millennials psychological, social, and behavioral factors towards willingness to adopt a digital detox using the Theory of Planned Behaviour framework. A structured questionnaire, including closed-ended Likert scale questions and open-ended questions from Millennials living in Singapore, the target research group, was obtained for quantitative analysis. Focus group interviews with customers and industry experts were conducted for qualitative analysis. The data obtained from quantitative analysis was analyzed using a statistical method, Statistical Package for Social Sciences. Descriptive statistics and inferential statistics were used to summarize respondents expectations in adopting the digital detox retreat. The data obtained from qualitative analysis were analyzed using the thematic analysis method. The results revealed that Well-being is the strongest variable, which is statistically significantly linked to attitude factors like self-love, and social media is less statistically significant compared to well-being, linked to positive subjective norm. In qualitative analysis, customers shared that the digital detox retreat helped in emotional healing and prioritizing activities. The study concludes with recommendations like collaborating with corporations and an implementation plan supported by cost-benefit analysis. This can help wellness retreat providers, marketers innovate their packages, improving the adoption rate of digital detox.

Key Words: Digital Detox, Millennials, Wellness, Singapore, Theory of Planned Behaviour, Social media influence.

1. INTRODUCTION

Mental health issues among young people in Singapore are increasing due to digital overuse. Anxiety is the most common problem faced by young people in Singapore. 27% of young people (1 in 4 young people) engage in excessive use of social media, which leads to extreme stress. Furthermore, 30.6% of people (aged 15-35 years) have severe or extremely severe symptoms of depression, anxiety, and stress. (2024) Institute of Mental Health NHG. "What interventions can help Millennials reduce their addiction to electronic devices and improve their mental health?" The popular solution is Digital detox retreats. These are open spaces where individuals set aside their devices and concentrate on self-care through meditation, yoga, silent sitting, or walking in forests. Singapore residents generally

travel to nearby countries like Bali (Indonesia), Thailand, India, Nepal, or Cambodia to experience pure digital detox retreats.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

The Theory of Planned Behavior was developed by Icek Ajzen in 1980. In this theory, we will be able to understand how individuals attitudes, subjective norms, and behavioral control influence consumers willingness to adopt the retreat.

- 1) Attitude towards behaviour considers variables such as well-being, quality of life, motivation, and mindfulness.
- 2) Subjective norms consider social media influence and sustainability.
- 3) Perceived behavioral control considers digital connection.

Millennial willingness to adopt a digital detox retreat Quaye, F.J. (2025). Willingness to try digital detox tourism comes from their wish to lower stress and boost their mental health.

Well-being and Quality of Life- While Bhatt, V.P. (2021) explains that when tourists are satisfied, their mental well-being increases, and they revisit the destination. Chen et al. (2021). There is a positive link between social media and subjective subjective well-being. When the subjective well-being of an individual is positive, they actively share their experience by posting their photos and videos on social media.

Motivation- Gan T (2023) explains that when internally there is a motivation to break the routine life, it leads to behavioral intention to explore wellness services that can help us to improve our mental wellness. Beautiful landscape, Natural attraction motivates people to choose the destination, and it creates behavioral intention to engage in wellness service.

Social Media- Quaye, F. J. (2025). Social media is the most important factor that helps to influence tourists to learn more about digital detox retreats, and it is used for marketing purposes.

Sustainable service- Scott A. Cohen (2014) Consumers care about how sustainable a product is, but they might still buy products that aren't sustainable.

Meditative mindfulness- Erore Sthapit (2023) Mindfulness is related to self-care, emotional regulation, and overall wellness can indirectly influence the behavioural intention for travelers decisions in wellness tourism.

3. RESEARCH DESIGN

3.1 Research Aim

To identify psychological, social, and environmental factors influencing the willingness of Millennials living in Singapore to adopt a digital detox retreat.

3.2 Research objectives

- 1) To understand the factors that increase the willingness of Millennials to participate in the digital detox retreat in Singapore and the Asia Pacific.
- 2) To evaluate mental wellness needs and adoption preferences of digital detox retreats.
- 3) Proposing marketing approaches, awareness campaigns, and corporate wellness initiatives based on evaluation findings.

3.3 Research problem

Despite growing awareness of mental health and burnout of Millennial participation and awareness in digital detox retreats remains limited. Wellness providers lack clear insights into psychological, social, and environmental factors influencing the willingness to adopt such a retreat.

3.4 Research Framework

Table 1 Research Framework

4. METHODOLOGIES

The study adopted a mixed-method approach by using qualitative interviews and quantitative surveys. Primary data was collected to understand the motivation and aspirations of Millennial customers in Singapore to adopt a digital detox retreat. The target segment belonged to Millennials in the age group of 29-44 years old, living in Singapore. Secondary data was collected in the form of a report, an article available online. A qualitative and quantitative survey was conducted. We adopted a purposive sampling method for focus group customer interviews, as we selected only Millennials who had experienced or were likely to experience a digital detox retreat. The research tries to understand the behavioral intention of millennials towards a digital detox retreat in Singapore. Millennials are people who were born between 1981 to 1996 (29 to 44 years old).

Table 2 Population of Singapore as of June 2024

Population of Singapore as of June 2024, by age group
(in 1,000s)

Interpretation: We have 945,330 Millennials living in Singapore. Krejce & Morgan table (1970) reflects that 9,45,330 millennials should have a sample size of 384.

Due to time and resource constraints, we managed to collect 121 responses, and among them, 75 respondents aged between 29 to 44 years old living in Singapore were selected. Data was collected through a structured questionnaire Google survey form consisting of closed-ended Likert scale questions and open-ended questions in Singapore. The questionnaire was divided into multiple sections, such as demographic information, willingness to attend a digital detox retreat depending upon various factors, recommendations to adopt a digital detox retreat, and suggestions for improvement. The data collected from the complete questionnaire were analyzed using statistical methods, Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS version 30). Descriptive statistics and multiple linear regression were used to summarize respondent’s expectations, experience in adopting digital detox retreats. Qualitative data was collected using focus group interviews with 11 customers and interviews with 6 industry experts. The small sample was collected due to constraints of time and resources. All the focus group interviews were conducted using Zoom, and audio conversations were recorded. Informed consent was obtained from all the respondents. The data collected was analyzed using the thematic analysis method facilitated by Atlas. ti software.

5. RESULTS

In this section the primary data was collected after surveys and interviews with respondents that are presented and analyzed.

Quantitative insights

5.1 Demographic characteristics of respondents

Table 3 Residential status in Singapore

Residential status in Singapore				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Dependent pass holder	14	18.7	18.7	18.7
Employment pass holder	26	34.7	34.7	53.3
LTVP	1	1.3	1.3	54.7
Permanent resident	15	20.0	20.0	74.7
Singaporean citizen	19	25.3	25.3	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: The highest number of respondents, comprising 34.7% are employment pass holders living in Singapore. This was followed by 25.3% who are Singaporean citizens. Additionally, 20% are permanent residents. Furthermore, 18.7% are dependent pass holders. This indicates that the majority of respondents are the working population.

Table 4 Gender distribution

Gender				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Female	35	46.7	46.7	46.7
Male	38	50.7	50.7	97.3
Prefer not to say	2	2.7	2.7	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: Most respondents are male, comprising 50.7%, followed by females, comprising 46.7%. This indicates balanced gender distribution.

Table 5 Employment status

Employment status				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Business owner	1	1.3	1.3	1.3
Employed	59	78.7	78.7	80.0
House Maker	3	4.0	4.0	84.0
Self employed	2	2.7	2.7	86.7
Student	1	1.3	1.3	88.0
Unemployed	9	12.0	12.0	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: The highest number of respondents are employed, comprising 78.7%. This indicates most respondents were a youthful demographic with stable income, likely to possess energy and willingness to attend a digital detox retreat.

Table 6 Ethnic Group

Ethnic group				
	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Bangladesh	1	1.3	1.3	1.3
Burmese	1	1.3	1.3	2.7
Chinese	12	16.0	16.0	18.7
Filipino	2	2.7	2.7	21.3
Indian	57	76.0	76.0	97.3
Prefer not to say	2	2.7	2.7	100.0
Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: The sample had a higher proportion of Indian respondents, 76%, as compared to the national average of 9% of the Singapore population (Singapore Department of Statistics, (2021). Singapore Population Statistics 2010-2020), followed by Chinese, comprising 16%. This can affect the generalization of the results to wider Millennial populations in Singapore.

5.2 Respondents connected to the devices

Table 7 Connected to a digital device, excluding work

Connected to digital device (excluding work)

		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	10 hours and more	10	13.3	13.3	13.3
	3 hours-6 hours	35	46.7	46.7	60.0
	7 hours-9 hours	15	20.0	20.0	80.0
	Less than 2 hours	15	20.0	20.0	100.0
	Total	75	100.0	100.0	

Interpretation: The highest number of respondents are connected to devices except during work hours for 3 hours to 6 hours, comprising 46.7%. This was followed by respondents connected for 7 hours to 9 hours, comprising 20%, and less than 2 hours, comprising 20%. This indicates the majority of respondents in the research use their devices for 3 hours to 6 hours daily, suggesting they spend a moderate amount of time with their devices.

5.3 Multiple Linear Regression Analysis

Table 8 Model Summary

Model Summary ^b									
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	R Square Change	Change Statistics			
						F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.878 ^a	.771	.754	1.383	.771	46.422	5	69	<.001

a. Predictors: (Constant), Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat due to its ecofriendly practices (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely), Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat due mental health concerns (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely), Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat due to its increase in your wellbeing? (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely), Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat due to social media influence (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely), Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat for their meditation courses?(1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely)

b. Dependent Variable: Willingness to attend digital detox retreat? (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely)

Interpretation: The variables were analyzed using multiple linear regression. A very strong positive correlation exists between the independent variables and the dependent variable. As the R value is at 0.878. R Square value comprises 0.771, so there is 77.1% variance in willingness to attend a digital detox retreat depending upon the independent variable's mental health concerns, increase in wellbeing, social media influence, eco-friendly practices, and meditation course. The significance value is less than 0.001, so the model is statistically significant.

Table 9 Anova table

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	443.968	5	88.794	46.422	<.001 ^b
	Residual	131.978	69	1.913		
	Total	575.947	74			

a. Dependent Variable: Willingness to attend digital detox retreat? (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely)

b. Predictors: (Constant), Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat due to its ecofriendly practices (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely), Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat due mental health concerns (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely), Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat due to its increase in your wellbeing? (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely), Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat due to social media influence (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely), Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat for their meditation courses?(1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely)

Interpretation: The Anova table comprises F-value = 46.422, and the p-value < .001 indicates that the regression model is highly statistically significant.

Table 10 Coefficients

Coefficients ^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	.346	.394		.879	.382
	Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat due to social media influence (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely)	.243	.118	.242	2.061	.043
	Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat due mental health concerns (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely)	.063	.100	.068	.631	.530
	Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat due to its increase in your wellbeing? (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely)	.297	.113	.302	2.621	.011
	Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat for their meditation courses?(1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely)	.201	.127	.214	1.577	.119
	Influenced to attend a digital detox retreat due to its ecofriendly practices (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely)	.129	.125	.138	1.033	.305

a. Dependent Variable: Willingness to attend digital detox retreat? (1 - Least likely, 10 - Most likely)

Interpretation: The influence of social media and an increase in well-being have a positive and significant influence on willingness to attend a digital detox retreat, as their p-values are less than 0.05. The influence to attend a digital detox retreat due to social media p-value (significant value) comprises 0.043. The influence on attending a digital detox retreat due to an increase in well-being p-value (significant value) comprises 0.011. While comparing respondents moving from Very likely (8) as an increase in well-being to almost certain (10), there is an increase in the number of people from 6 to 7 people. This can lead to a change in health behavior. In the real world, we can increase millennials wellbeing by introducing initiatives like mindfulness programs and creating awareness about mental health. While comparing respondents moving from Somewhat likely (6) as an increase in well-being to almost certain (10), there is an increase in the number of people from 5 to 6 people. Fear of missing out or anxiety can encourage millennials to adopt digital detox retreats; similarly, social

media can promote digital detox retreats using influencers and health trends. Comparing the beta value of social media influence and the increase in well-being. The influence to attend a digital detox due to an increase in wellbeing has a higher beta value at 0.297 than social media influence at 0.243. We can conclude that an increase in well-being is a strong and significant positive influence on willingness to attend a digital detox retreat, and the influence of social media has a significant positive influence on willingness to attend a digital detox retreat. In today's world, by using authentic storytelling and personalized social campaigns, social media can influence millennials to adopt a digital detox retreat. All other variables like mental health concern, meditation course, and eco-friendly practices have a p-value (significance value) higher than 0.05; they are not statistically significant with willingness to attend a digital detox retreat.

Qualitative Insights

Findings of the interview with customers

Motivation to escape stress- Participants were undergoing emotional turbulence, work-related stress, mental health, and life pressure; they also needed self-care. These factors influenced them to participate in a digital detox retreat.

Wellbeing self-awareness- All millennials experienced emotional healing, self-love, mindfulness, and they had multiple takeaways that positively influenced them to participate in Digital detox retreats.

Quality of life- Participants participating in digital detox can manage workload, have a clear work-life balance, and significantly improve mental health. With the help of things factors, their quality of life improves. This helps to create a balanced lifestyle.

Social media impact- There are mixed reactions on whether millennials are influenced by social media. They are influenced if they are motivated to engage in it, or it is of interest to them, or the travelling group is known to the millennial. A few millennials are not active on social media, so they are not influenced by social media posts.

Sustainability impact- There is a mixed reaction towards the influence of sustainable practices among digital detox retreats. Many millennials believe their decision to choose a digital detox retreat will not be influenced by retreats practicing sustainable services. Few of them believe there is a lack of awareness, so they don't know about sustainable practices, and some of them will be influenced as they are emotionally aligned with sustainability.

Impact due to meditative mindfulness- Mindfulness practice in digital detox retreat positively impacts millennial participants during the retreat. They have clarity of thought, are peaceful, have emotional awareness, and engage in deeper discovery about themselves.

Findings from the interview with industry experts

Motivation to escape stress- Participants can be encouraged to join a digital detox using fear-based motivation, a burnout situation, internal realization, and to break away from routine activities. While marketing for digital detox retreats, we have to create more awareness about mental health to attract customers who will be attracted by fear-based influence and the self-realization of customers. For individuals in a burnout situation who want to break away, more focus should be given on healing messages.

Well-being and quality of life- While looking at all the above factors like fear-based impact, positive state of mind, mental awareness, different healing techniques, and shift in wellness energy, positive influences millennials to attend digital detox retreats. Motivated people come back to digital detox retreats and experience positive emotional satisfaction. They also recommend digital detox retreats to other people.

Social media impact- Millennials believe in shared experiences that are validated by authentic comments of social media influencers. If positive comments are shared by influencers about a digital detox retreat, millennials prefer to visit that retreat.

Sustainability impact- There are mixed reactions from industry experts on whether millennials prefer sustainable practices are not. When a millennial is environmentally aware, they will be more inclined to adopt retreats with sustainable practices. For others, it adds value, and for some of them, it doesn't matter if any retreat is eco-friendly or not.

Impact due to meditative mindfulness- Meditative mindfulness practice in digital detox should be personalized and curated depending upon individuals' mental capability. Meditative mindfulness helps millennials to reduce stress levels and improve overall well-being.

6. DISCUSSION

The study investigates the factors that influence millennials willingness to attend a digital detox retreat in Singapore. We combined both quantitative analysis and qualitative insights using focus group interviews and expert interviews. They align with the Theory of Planned Behavior, Ajzen (1991), exploring attitudes, behavioral control, and subjective norms. The key findings explore the relationship between factors like social

media, sustainable practices, sustainability values, and mindful practices in adopting a digital detox retreat.

In terms of attitude, millennials revealed that their strong motivational drivers are burnout, workplace stress, and the intention of self-care, which validates the Theory of Planned Behavior. The most significant variable is the increase in well-being, which affirms that Millennials prefer mental health benefits over other wellness ideas.

In terms of subjective norms, social media influence is one of the most important factors that validates the Theory of Planned Behaviour, which influences the adoption of a digital detox retreat. On one hand, it may contribute to digital overdose, and on the other hand, it also persuades individuals to participate in digital detox retreats using peer testimonials, influencer endorsements. Respondents are willing to adopt a digital detox retreat when they are motivated by a trusted peer or due to activities that are aligned with activities like mindfulness. In terms of perceived behavioural control, qualitative interviews highlighted that participants attending the retreats previously experienced immense improvement in wellbeing, focus, and stress management, which validates the Theory of Planned Behaviour influencing the adoption of a digital detox retreat. The sample consists of well-educated millennials living in employment pass and Singaporeans, suggesting they are likely exposed to digital demands. However, the excess representation of Indians, 76%, among the sample group makes it harder to apply across Singapore's diverse millennial population. The gender distribution is balanced. Most respondents reveal they moderately use digital devices for 3 hours to 6 hours, in contrast very small segment reveals they heavily use digital devices for 7 hours to 9 hours. So, more screen time didn't significantly impact the willingness to attend, as the chi-square p-value was 0.238. The finding reveals how much digital fatigue matters more to people than the number of hours spent on the devices.

Industry experts cautioned that not all mindfulness practice programs are suitable for everyone, especially people suffering from serious mental disorders, so customized mindfulness practices will be helpful for these individuals. Even though globally people emphasize sustainability, eco-friendly practices didn't significantly impact willingness to adopt a digital detox retreat in the regression analysis. Qualitative customer interviews indicated that some millennials are aligned with sustainable values, and most respondents preferred high-quality content of preferred activities compared to environmentally friendly activities. Experts mentioned that sustainability can be an important driver for Millennials who value on sustainability than on other factors.

Meditative mindfulness positively helped millennials by enhancing emotional clarity and calmness. In regression analysis, it didn't significantly influence millennials to adopt a digital detox retreat. It proves that meditative mindfulness is not a motivator, but it enhances the satisfaction level of participants. As per the theory of planned behavior, meditative mindfulness helps to retain participants post the retreat; it doesn't drive respondents to adopt a digital detox retreat unless we specify that participants will receive tangible outcomes like stress reduction. Qualitative responses indicated mixed reactions from participants due to digital disconnection, such as fear of missing out, to relaxation, highlighting the difficulty of unplugging devices in the current society. We understand the importance of guided disconnection by clearly communicating the benefits of overcoming digital anxiety.

7. ANALYSIS & INTERPRETATION

The research helps to understand the behavior of Millennials to adopt a digital detox retreat using the theory of Planned Behavior. The various factors, like attitude, subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control, are checked with primary data (qualitative and quantitative methods) and secondary research.

1) Research objective to understand the factors that increase the willingness of Millennials to participate in the digital detox retreat – Well-being is the strongest variable among quantitative analysis, with a p-value of 0.011. Qualitative feedback from customers and experts also highlighted emotional healing and self-love, which are important factors in well-being. In the case of secondary research, well-being aligns with the attitude factor of The Theory of Planned Behavior and research from Sophie Thorne .2021 and Chen et al. 2021 that connects healthy living to behavioral intention.

Implications- By using this research study, they will be able to create strategies that can focus on tangible results like stress relief and better sleep.

2) Research objective to evaluate mental wellness needs and adoption preferences of digital detox retreats- In the qualitative study, Motivational factors like burnout and self-care were highlighted, but in the quantitative analysis, motivation had a poor impact on willingness to adopt a digital detox retreat, with a p-value of 0.530 it shows a gap between behavioral intention and action of Millennials. This can happen due to limitations of time or cost.

Implications- There seems to be motivation, but to change from interest to action, we will need to offer trial-based and affordable retreats.

3) Research objective in proposing marketing approaches, awareness campaigns, and corporate wellness initiatives based on evaluation findings- As per quantitative analysis, social media significantly impacts willingness to adopt a digital detox retreats, showing a p-value of 0.043 this aligns with Theory of planned behavior subjective norms factor and research from Xie-Carson (2024) and Ye Chen (2021) that highlights influencers and peer reviews impact Millennials decisions. As per experts suggestions in marketing campaigns, authentic experiences must be showcased to attract more Millennials.

Implications- The marketing campaigns can be enhanced by including experiential experiences of influencers and positive customer feedback

Contradictions and Gaps from findings

As per a quantitative study, motivation due to mental health concerns, meditative mindfulness, and eco-friendly practices doesn't significantly influence willingness to adopt a digital detox retreat, but qualitative analysis emphasized that eco-friendly practices are important for eco-friendly Millennials. Motivation due to mental health does not significantly influence willingness. This may be because mental health is considered taboo, so they wouldn't mention that they want to attend a retreat due to mental health. Sustainability doesn't significantly influence as it is not the deciding factor for the majority of the population. Meditative mindfulness wouldn't have significantly impacted as people would have experienced meditation at home using apps like Headspace, and they don't want to spend on retreats. Experts suggested personalization of meditative practices, as it may not be suitable for all individuals with varied mental health conditions.

Implications- Eco-friendly practice and meditative mindfulness encourage customer retention that leads to loyalty, but they may not motivate first-time customers.

8. RECOMMENDATION

The strategic recommendations that can be proposed to increase awareness and adoption rate of digital detox retreat among millennials are:

1) Awareness through testimonials- Millennials prefer retreats promoted by experiential influences and peer testimonials. We can promote using these techniques to create an authentic experience and build trust among consumers. We can promote the behind-the-scenes videos of retreats using YouTube, Instagram, and TikTok.

2) Mental wellness support- During the retreat, guided meditation, wellness counselling, and personalized assessment can be provided to the customers. We can hire

a famous and licensed wellness practitioner to enhance the credibility of our packages.

3) Eco-friendly practices as value add- Some retreats only consider eco-friendly practices as the primary driver for their retreat and ignore the activities available in the retreat that led to unsatisfied customers who will not revisit the retreat, so the digital detox retreat's main aim is to provide interesting activities, and they can use sustainability as a value add. Retreats involved in eco-friendly practices can apply for green-key certification and use it for promotion.

4) Collaborate with corporates- Digital detox retreat organizers can collaborate with corporates and offer tailored packages to the employees with flexible pricing. They can offer a discount to family members of employees.

9. IMPLEMENTATION PLAN

1) Awareness campaign- We can launch an awareness campaign using peer testimonials on social media and collaborating with influencers, promoting experiential travel. The timeline will be 1 to 2 months. The resources that are required will be a marketing budget and video tools. The marketing team will be responsible for these campaigns.

2) Mental health wellness support- We can provide customized support using wellness practitioners and coaches during the retreat. During pre-retreat and post-retreat, we can converse with customers to understand their experiences. The timeline will be 3 to 4 months. The resources required will be consultants and a budget for wellness practitioners. The human resource team will be responsible for this support.

3) Eco-friendly practices- We must include eco-friendly practices in our brochures to attract eco-friendly customers. It will be an ongoing process. The resources required will be eco-friendly materials and regular vendor checks.

4) Corporate collaboration- We first identify the companies that can be mid or large organizations with a high-stress environment, like finance and health sectors, and depending upon the problem, we offer customized packages and receive feedback post-retreat sessions. The timeline will be 1 month to ongoing. The team involved will be the business development, sales, marketing, and finance teams.

10. COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

For the above strategic recommendations these are the cost-benefit analysis.

1) **Awareness through testimonials-** By creating awareness using testimonials, we will be spending approximately SGD1500 (influencer content and collaboration), and we will have the benefit of reaching approximately 40000 views in a month using platforms like Instagram, TikTok, and YouTube. So, the cost is low, and the benefit is high. It can be useful for all new and current companies.

2) **Mental wellness support-** The support by well-known practitioners can incur a cost of approximately SGD 5000, but the benefit is high, as it can add a premium value of 10%. So, the cost is high, but the benefit is high. It can be useful for established large brands.

3) **Eco-friendly practices as a value add-** This will incur a cost of approximately SGD 1000, and we will be able to increase the trust by 5%. So, the cost is low, but the benefit is low.

4) **Collaborate with corporates-** We will incur a cost of approximately SGD 1500, and we will be able to reach around 600 employees per month. So, the cost is high, but the benefit is high. It can be useful for established large brands.

11. CONCLUSION

This research explains that the framework Theory of Planned Behavior was utilized to understand the willingness to attend digital detox retreats of Millennials living in Singapore. Out of 121 responses, we selected 75 millennial respondents to study their motivational drivers and challenges in adopting a digital detox retreat.

The hypothesis supported the following conclusion:

1) Well-being and quality of life (H1)- We can accept the hypothesis that the positive impact of well-being and quality of life positively influences Millennials willingness to adopt a digital detox retreat. Organizers can highlight outcomes like stress relief, emotional balance, and relaxation in their marketing materials to attract millennial customers.

2) Motivation due to mental health concern (H2)- We don't accept the hypothesis that higher motivation positively influences Millennials willingness to adopt a digital detox retreat. Even though motivation is high, people may or may not be interested in adopting a digital detox retreat.

We will need to remove barriers like excessive cost, a lack of awareness that prevent millennials from adopting a digital detox retreat.

3) Social media influence (H3)- We can accept the hypothesis that social media influence positively impacts Millennials willingness to adopt digital detox retreats. Posts by experiential influencers, testimonials, and authentic reviews posted on Instagram, TikTok can positively influence millennials to adopt a digital detox retreat.

4) Sustainable service (H4)- We don't accept the hypothesis that higher awareness of sustainable service increases Millennials willingness to adopt a digital detox retreat. Greater emphasis is placed on activities as compared to sustainable service, so millennials may or may not be influenced to adopt a digital detox retreat due to sustainable practices adopted in a retreat. These can be termed as value add instead of selling it on a standalone basis.

5) Meditative mindfulness (H5)- We don't accept the hypothesis that meditative mindfulness practices positively influence Millennials willingness to adopt a digital detox retreat. The influence of meditative mindfulness on the digital detox retreat is based on an individual basis. We cannot generalize that all meditative mindfulness positively influences all individuals, especially people suffering from severe mental health conditions; it may not be helpful for them. We must personalize it as per individual comfort.

The findings reflected that even though there is ample digital overload and mental health concerns are prevalent, the most significant factor predicting willingness to attend such retreats is an increase in well-being and social media influence. Other factors, like sustainability and digital usage, were less significant.

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Nil

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APPENDIX

1.1 Extracts from interview with Focus group customers

Customer insights
and industry experts c

1.2 Customer Data Set

Data set.xlsx